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WAYS TO IMPROVE PERSONNEL POLICY IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF FINANCIAL SERVICES PROVIDED BY FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich

Samarkand Branch of Tashkent state university of Economics

ORCID: 0009-0006-8449-3050

Annotatsiya: Currently, in the context of the process of liberalization of financial institutions of the country, one of the important issues is the successful implementation of personnel policy. This article provides feedback and proposals on ways to improve staffing policies to ensure the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.

Kalit so'zlar: financial institution, financial service, employee, personnel policy, bank.

Abstract: Hozirgi kunda, mamlakatning moliyaviy muassasalarini liberallashtirish jarayonida muhim masalalardan biri bu kadrlar siyosatini muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirishdir. Ushbu maqolada moliyaviy muassasalar tomonidan taqdim etilayotgan moliyaviy xizmatlarning sifatini ta'minlash maqsadida kadrlar siyosatini yaxshilash yo'llari bo'yicha fikrlar va takliflar keltirilgan.

Key words: moliyaviy muassasa, moliyaviy xizmat, xodim, kadrlar siyosati, bank.

Аннотация: В настоящее время, в контексте процесса либерализации финансовых учреждений страны, одним из важных вопросов является успешная реализация кадровой политики. В данной статье представлены отзывы и предложения по улучшению кадровой политики с целью обеспечения качества финансовых услуг, предоставляемых финансовыми учреждениями.

Ключевые слова: финансовое учреждение, финансовая услуга, сотрудник, кадровая политика, банк.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the process of further liberalization of the role of financial institutions in the country is underway. The main purpose of this process is to expand the range of services provided by financial services and increase the confidence of customers in financial institutions.

It is true that the effectiveness of financial services aimed at the development of the country have an impact on the development of all sectors of the economy. Improving the reliability and security of financial services, increasing the speed of service delivery, the development of customers, both quantitatively and qualitatively, bring great benefits to the country.

The development of financial and economic relations in the context of anti-crisis management, changes in the form of ownership and organizational subordination in financial institutions make it necessary to constantly intensify the implementation of an effective mechanism of the concept of financial services. In this regard, the perfect conduct of personnel policy is a topical issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Economist Peter Rose stresses the bank as a financial services firm. It includes such financial services as financial resource management, consumer credit, cash flow management, leasing and other services that reflect banking activities [1].

F. Kotler pointed out that one of our activities (in our case, the bank is any event or service that the bank offers any operation to the other (bank customers). At the same time, financial and banking services are specialized commodity of financial and banking institutions, and as any commercial enterprise, it strives to achieve the maximum volume of its implementation. With increasing competition between commercial banks and certain groups of financial intermediaries, we should raise the issue of developing the system of financial and banking services as a goal-oriented, clearly targeted activity.

According to Z.Ahrorov and others, financial services represent a set of socio-economic relations of legal entities and individuals related to the formation of funds in the banking, insurance, leasing and investment markets, as well as in other financial relationships [3]. Therefore, the effective implementation of financial services provides a positive solution to many processes. In particular, it improves the quality of life of the population through the provision of financial resources to legal entities and individuals, access to savings, insurance of the population and business against various risks and the provision of other important services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article methods of analysis-synthesis, statistical analysis, and scientific observation is used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The provision of enterprises of various industries with modern tools and technological equipment, the provision of the volume and quality of services can be done by increasing the activity of financial services in the industry. At the same time, financial institutions should take the initiative, and the organization of systematic service activities of economic entities should be an important issue in this area. As a result, all the work related to the full and quality satisfaction of the demand for the services of a financial institution (finance, banking, insurance, tax, etc.) can be combined into a single set of processes.

Clearly, banks need to expand their asset and liability operations. The banking services associated with the passive operations of the bank, mainly the types of deposits of the bank and their growing number, indicate the development of interaction between banks and customers, especially new customers, mainly the population. Deposit balances in banks across the country are growing from year to year. This indicates that the confidence of the majority of the population in the national currency and the banking system is growing.

The mechanism of effective introduction of financial services determines the effectiveness of individual measures and a set of measures to be taken by the state to ensure the achievement of the goals set by the system of financial institutions.

Financial institutions have sufficient conditions for the implementation of service strategies, and it is expedient to list them (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Adequate conditions for the implementation of the strategy of services in financial institutions.

However, despite this, the activity of financial institutions is not observed. There are several specific reasons for this, one of the main of which is that both financial institutions and customers using their services, as well as investors are adequately equipped with modern methodologies for assessing the position, opportunities and investment attractiveness of the financial market [4].

At the same time, one of the biggest tasks facing banks is to bring in additional income after the development of new types of deposits for a certain amount of expenses. In addition, deposits are often duplicated, i.e. the type of deposit introduced by one bank is put into circulation by another bank a month later with some changes. There are some problems in bringing the types of deposits to the attention of customers and explaining their features, because banks do not pay much attention to the advertising of their products.

One of the main systems of bank management is public relations, a system of establishing relationships between the bank and the public, their development and the establishment of good ideas about the bank in the public consciousness. This system is used in the banking system in many countries around the world. Currently, the country is struggling for every customer, especially for financially stable customers, which, in turn, creates the basis for increased interbank competition. Therefore, each bank must operate using management principles so as not to lose competition. Moreover, this does not begin without the use of public relations. The bank is struggling to increase their number and ensure sustainable growth for the customer. In the market of banking services, the republic will offer services or products related to the active operations of commercial banks, mainly short-term and long-term loans.

There are some problems in the commercial banks of the country on this issue, ie the majority of loans are non-repayable. In the activities of banks, it is observed that loans are not issued without analyzing the financial condition of the client or in which market segment he operates and his future position. Similar loans will not be repaid in the end, which will inevitably lead to an increase in bank costs.

It is known that the lending process is one of the specific processes with the highest level of risk. Therefore, this process must be completed with analysis. Bank management is the art of governing power and management, special skills and administrative skills in resource management. In other words, management is the management of resources, the management of people. Knowing how to operate effectively and profit is the process of multiplying it. In this sense, management is a decision-making and monitoring of its implementation, which requires a certain high art and skill.

Personnel management is a system of interconnected organizational, economic and social measures to develop and effectively use the potential of people employed in the enterprise, to create the necessary conditions for their normal operation.

Such management:

Functional - issues directly related to the solution of personnel issues, ie personnel selection, dismissal, training, salaries, etc .;

Organizational management includes all persons and institutions directly responsible for personnel work, ie managers, personnel department, trade unions and others.

A large amount of technical knowledge is required from the heads of departments to help bank employees to work with complex banking products. In addition, management skills are required from these managers to ensure that employees display their best qualities at work.

The main changes in the organization of labor in a modern bank explain the need to take into account aspects of internal and external activities, not only consumer priorities, but also the needs and preferences of employees.

The high level of self-awareness and education of bank employees leads to the fact that the effectiveness of theological methods of labor organization is declining. In particular, the importance of economic components in the motivation of labor activity is declining, while the main part of the population of developed countries in the West is relatively well-off.

Foreign experience shows that there are new opportunities for customer service - innovative services - Internet banking and home banking. In the experience of our country, these forms of services could be provided by the People's Bank, but today our banks do not have any experience in the strategy of the Internet banking market, which in itself does not allow the widespread development of Internet banking. The reasons hindering the development of Internet banking services may be the lack of public confidence in the banking system, insufficient security of transactions via the Internet, the low level of computerization of the population and the widespread use of the Internet. However, there is a problem in the banks themselves, many of them are not able to develop innovative services even after the installation of Internet banking equipment, as a result, it is impossible to hide Internet services to special business managers of projects. In our opinion, the establishment of control over such projects by the staff of the information technology service will help to eliminate the existing shortcomings.

The development of innovative banking services largely depends on the method of pricing for these services, in addition, it is important to take into account the role of banking in the process of their specialization.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, in the context of economic reforms in the country and the growing interbank competition, the position and future of each bank depends primarily on the personnel working in it. Therefore, in recent years, personnel policy in banks focuses on such important measures as the selection and placement of personnel, the constant recruitment and renewal of young, knowledgeable, economists, filling vacancies with qualified personnel, working with reserves.

This, in turn, will expand the banking services provided by commercial banks to customers and expand the role of banks in the implementation of reforms in the country.

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Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
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